

THE DEVELOPMENT OF METAL END-FITTINGS FOR AXIALLY LOADED COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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Simple efficient fittings have been made which can load fibre-reinforced pultrusions to their ultimate strengths. A novel fabrication process incorporating crimping and bonding techniques has been evolved, and a simple design procedure for coaxial bonded joints suggested. The performance of the fittings as manufactured and after environmental exposure is described.

INTRODUCTION

Many structures contain axially loaded rod or tube elements. A common example is the unit of space-frames that are frequently employed, in e.g. roofs and beams, to obtain large spans. However, one disadvantage of the conventional metal tube is the dead load of the structure itself.

Pultruded fibre reinforced plastics suggest a more efficient route. They give a highly oriented composite of well controlled volume fraction with reproducible mechanical properties. On a weight basis, they are axially stronger, and, in the case of carbon fibre composites, stiffer than the common structural metals such as steel and aluminium alloys. The main problem with these highly anisotropic materials is their low shear strength parallel to the fibres, frequently about 5% of the composite tensile strength measured in the fibre direction. Load diffusion into these materials requires care, and much effort has been expended (1) in developing efficient methods of so doing.

Adhesive bonded joints are preferred for jointing composites since they reduce the tendency towards composite shear failure as compared with mechanically fastened joints. Such bonded joints have been shown to be more efficient on a weight basis than mechanical joints in prototype CFRP space-frames using pultruded rod and tube, (2,3), but the designs used so far have limitations in strength and ease of final assembly.

The aim of this work was to develop improved fittings for use on aligned reinforced plastics tube, such that the derived structural elements could be assembled on site. Two designs were studied, a threaded connector and a pin connector, both requiring only conventional tools for final fabrication. Additionally, a simple butt joint was developed for structural connection of pultruded tubes. Attention was paid to low cost manufacture and design simplicity to assist the user.

FITTING DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

In the coaxial bonded joint arrangement under study, the loading is predominantly in the desirable shear mode. However, the relative flexibility of the adhesive to that of the adherends affects stress distribution and stress concentrations exist at the ends of a bonded overlap loaded in shear. Although a linear relationship exists between the failure load of a joint and bond width, the relationship between failure load and bond overlap length is neither simple nor linear. Analyses exist (e.g. 4,5) for estimating in-plane and out-of-plane stresses in simple joints, but are of limited use for practical designs where adherends of unlike elastic moduli and unequal thickness may be encountered.

The historical approach to designing bonded joints is based on the 'joint factor' method, as in the classical work of De Bruyne (6). Here the fall off in the load-carrying capacity of a joint as overlap length increases is expressed as a correlation between average shear strength in the adhesive and the ratio of overlap length to adherend thickness (the 'joint factor'). Using test specimens bonded and loaded in a manner similar to that of the intended assembly, a correlation diagram between shear strength and joint factor can be established to calculate optimum parameters of joint dimensions, mean adhesive shear stress and the mean adherend tensile stress. This method relies on a large data base for the correlation diagram, and becomes invalid if joint variables change, e.g. type of adhesive or adherend, adherend surface preparation technique, adhesive thickness or cure temperature and pressure, and joint environmental exposure.

The approach has obvious limitations, and more recently exact analytical models of bonded joints have been used for designing with composites. The stress concentrations arising from the shear lag mechanisms have been studied by many workers mainly using finite element elastic stress analysis and incorporating closed form solutions, (e.g. 7,8,9,10 and 11). Adherend displacements should be matched across the bond line for efficiency over sensible bond lengths, for example by changing adherend stiffness progressively along the overlap length. This can be done by altering

thickness, or, by directly tailoring the adherend material properties (12). Since structural adhesives exhibit viscoelastic behaviour, shear lag analyses have been extended to take into account this non-linear elastic behaviour (13), in particular the ability of adhesives to accommodate differential adherend shear strains (14). However, these analyses only apply to a few simple geometries, and require knowledge of adhesive properties such as shear modulus and elastic and 'plastic' shear strain, which are not usually amongst those quoted in adhesives manufacturers' property data.

A further complication arises from the observed reduction in joint shear strength as bondline thickness increases. For thermosetting structural adhesives the highest shear strengths are usually achieved with bond lines in the thickness range 20 - 150 μm . A thin glue line has more resistance to failure on joint flexure, since larger forces are necessary to deform a thin adhesive film than a thick one. Further, the thicker glue lines probably contain voids or air bubbles or other failure initiation sites. The requirement for thin bond lines means that structural joints require precision machining to achieve their optimum performance, an expensive and time consuming process.

It was decided, therefore, to design the coaxial joint fittings on a semi-empirical basis in the absence of a specific analysis for a coaxial joint with a fibre reinforced composite adherend and a thin bond line. Scaling effects made the analysis in (15), in which a coaxial joint between a GRP pultruded rod and a metal sleeve used a thick layer of potting material as an adhesive, quite inappropriate. A manufacturing method was required that could use stock size material, with no precision machining, and yet would still achieve the desirable thin bond line. It has been shown (16) that crimped-on metal end fittings can be surprisingly efficient when applied to pultruded GRP rod. It was thus decided that a combination of the two technologies, i.e. crimping a metal tube onto a composite element, with a fluid adhesive interfay subsequently cured, might give low cost and a thin bond line, and was worthy of in-depth study. A parallel study into weight-optimised precision machined fitments was also undertaken.

DETAIL FITTING DESIGN

The objective was to develop fittings for use on a stock size pultruded CFRP tube. The tubing chosen was 8 mm o.d., 6.6 mm i.d., containing 65% by volume of Type A-S Fibre in an 828/MNA/BDMA epoxy resin matrix, (a stock item of Courtaulds Limited). Quoted mechanical properties are :- Tensile Strength 1.5 GPa, Tensile Modulus 110 GPa and Interlaminar Shear Strength 65 MPa. A tensile failure force for this tube was calculated at 24.1 kN, this value being used for design purposes.

Aluminium alloys seemed the most appropriate materials for manufacturing light weight fittings. The large thermal expansion mismatch with CFRP mitigates against the use of hot curing adhesive and a cold or warm curing adhesive was desirable, with good gap-filling properties. A review of cold curing structural paste adhesives (17) indicated that Redux 410 adhesive, supplied by Ciba-Geigy Limited, would meet the requirements, and this adhesive was used for the bulk of the work herein. The 12.7 mm overlap shear strength quoted in (17) for this adhesive is 25 MPa.

Crimped and Bonded Fittings

A crimping die was designed for conforming stock size aluminium alloy tubing (12.7 mm O.D., 9.5 mm bore) onto an 8 mm diameter inner element, with a suitable allowance for the desired glue line thickness. This die was constructed out of 0.4% carbon, 1% manganese steel to BS En 8, and is shown in Fig. 1, together with a length of crimped tube. A radiused tool was manufactured to flatten the non-crimped end of the tube, leaving an area for drilling to accommodate pin-connectors, as shown in Fig. 2. To allow for the non-linearity of adhesive shear strength as a function of increased overlap length, a design value of mean adhesive shear stress of 18 MPa was used, i.e. 30% less than the reported 12.7 mm overlap shear strength. It was calculated that a 50 mm overlap was required to sustain the 24.1 kN design load.

The necessary 24.1 kN load could be sustained by a high strength (UTS 460 MPa) aluminium alloy tube of the desired dimensions, or by a similarly sized medium strength (UTS 240 MPa) aluminium alloy tube in combination with a 6.35 mm diameter medium strength aluminium alloy rod bonded into the bore of the CFRP tube and extended into the flattened portion. Both options were assessed experimentally.

Turned and Threaded Fittings

These fittings were designed to be machined from high strength (UTS 500 MPa) 12.7 mm diameter aluminium alloy bar, initially using a 50 mm bonded overlap length. The bore would be machined to achieve a bond line thickness in the range 50 - 150 μm . Bosses externally threaded to $\frac{1}{4}$ " BSW would be used, with the boss bored out internally and the fitting turned down externally to reduce weight as far as possible, retaining sufficient material to sustain the 24.1 kN design load. Design of an internally threaded fitment would also be explored.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

It was found impossible to crimp and flatten aluminium alloy tubing in the as-received condition without cracking, which was far more marked in the high strength tubing. Consequently, tubing was used in the solution treated condition. The medium strength alloy, Al, 1% Mg, 1% Si, 0.5% Mn, to specification HT 30, was solution treated at 530°C for 1 hour and cold water quenched. The high strength alloy, Al, 4.4% Cu, 0.7% Mg, 0.8% Si, 0.75% Mn, to specification L105, was solution treated at 505°C for 2 hours and cold water quenched. Turned and threaded fittings were manufactured from bar to specification HE 15 TF (equivalent in composition to L105) in the as-received condition, and received no heat treatment.

All fitting components were given a bonding pre-treatment as follows :-

- 1) Vapour degrease in 1.1.1. Trichloroethane for 2 hours.
- 2) Chromic-sulphuric acid etch by a method conforming to Method O of U.K. Ministry of Defence Specification Def. Stan. O3-2. The chromic-sulphuric acid etch bath temperature was reduced to 55°C to minimise age-hardening of the solution treated tubes during etching.
- 3) Oven dry for about 15 minutes at 60°C.
- 4) Bond within 1 hour of step 3.

The condition of the chromic-sulphuric acid bath was periodically checked by making and testing conventional 12.7 mm overlap shear samples using L73 alloy.

Surface pre-treatment of the CFRP tube was limited to thorough wet abrasion using silicon carbide paper, and successive wipes with ketone soaked tissues until no further debris was removed. Recent studies (18,19 and 20) have shown this simple technique to be very satisfactory in terms both of initial strength and environmental durability of the resultant bonded joint.

Joints were assembled within 1 hour of mixing the 2-component adhesive. For the threaded fittings, fine nylon line (160 μm diameter) spaced at 90° intervals around the fitting circumference was used as an assembly aid, as in (2). No form of bond-line control was used in the crimped fittings. The ends of the fittings were plugged with modelling clay or rubber bungs, and the fittings were oven-cured at 60°C, overnight. This procedure assisted in achieving a sound bond line, since it was evident that the expansion of trapped air within the CFRP tube had increased the adhesive spew fillet at the end of the fitment, during oven-cure.

The stock size CFRP tube could not be supplied, and a sub-standard batch with an off-centre 5.8 mm bore was used for the test programme. The calculated failure force for this tube is 35.8 kN, such that the fitments as designed are not capable of failing the CFRP in tension. For crimped fittings with a central rod, the rod

was turned down to a clearance fit within the CFRP tube for the required overlap length. The tendency for the CFRP tube to split during crimping when no central rod was used was overcome by limiting the crimping force to about 70 kN. This limit was later used for all crimped fittings including those with central rods.

The fittings were tested in a screw-driven 100 kN capacity Instron testing machine at a displacement rate of 1 mm/minute.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

During evolution of the fittings, several significant points emerged for each fitting type. These are summarised together with the test data for the optimised fittings as follows :-

Crimped and Bonded Fittings

Cracking of the alloy tubing during crimping and flattening could be suppressed almost completely in the HT30 alloy by correct solution heat treatment. Even after treatment, the L105 alloy displayed gross cracking at the edge of the flattened portion as shown in Fig. 3 (bottom specimen), that would be unacceptable in a production item. Consequently, it was decided to use HT30 tubing for end fittings with an additional central rod, and L105 tubing for butt fittings without a central rod.

Some cracking always occurred in the crimped portion of the aluminium alloy tube, as shown in the sectioned fittings in Figs. 4 and 5. This cracking was more extensive in the L105 alloy which conformed more closely to the CFRP tube than the HT30 alloy. The thinner bond line in the L105 alloy fittings gave the necessary load bearing capacity using a shorter overlap length than with fittings made with HT30 alloy. A brief investigation into the effect of overlap length on fitment pull-off force indicated that a 45 mm overlap was required for L105 alloy crimped fittings, and a 50 mm or greater overlap was necessary for HT30 alloy crimped fittings using the additional central rod.

For HT30 crimped fittings using a central rod, the best results were achieved when the overlap length inside the CFRP tube was less than, or equal to, the outer overlap length. When the inner overlap was longer than the outer overlap, low failure loads were observed. The usual failure mode was for the inner rod to debond initially, followed by yield and failure of the alloy tube between the crimped and flattened portions, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (centre specimen).

It was found better to crimp the alloy tube prior to flattening; the converse procedure produced a lower strength fitting. Inspection of Fig. 2, in which the centre fitting was crimped prior to flattening and the outer two fittings were flattened prior to crimping indicates why. In the latter two fittings, a flared end is visible on the crimp as a result of the crimping tool bearing onto a partly flattened tube. This causes a more pronounced stress concentration at the end of the crimp and a reduction in the area of effective load bearing metal at the crimp end, leading to the premature failure illustrated.

A few tests were performed to determine the contribution of friction to the strength of the crimped and bonded joints. 50 mm overlap HT30 alloy fittings crimped onto the CFRP tube at a press force of 67 kN with no adhesive failed at low forces of the order of 100 N, and could usually be pulled off by hand. It is considered that friction makes a minimal contribution to the strength of crimped and bonded fittings, and that the value of the crimping process lies in the formation of a thin bond line without the need for precise machining.

Many crimped and bonded fittings were sectioned, and in no case was starvation of the bond line at the point of crimping force application observed. It is possible that starvation might occur if a less viscous adhesive than Redux 410 were used, when ballotini or other means of glue line thickness control could be incorporated.

In cases where a bond failed, inspection of the adherend surfaces showed that a failure was usually 100% cohesive in the CFRP. In a few cases where faulty pre-treatment of either adherend was suspected, some adhesive failure was observed. The usual cohesive failure of the CFRP was by shear; a thin layer of CFRP was left attached to the aluminium adherend(s) following failure.

The results obtained with 45 mm overlap butt fittings and 50 mm overlap end fittings are given in Tables 1 and 2. Exposure specimens were immersed in deionized water at $51 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2000 hours prior to test, and were weighed before and after conditioning. Random positive and negative weight changes occurred, in all cases less than 0.15% of total specimen mass. Some pitting corrosion of the alloy fittings occurred during conditioning, and the adhesive spew fillet changed colour from bright yellow to a dull brown while retaining surface gloss. Specimens were tested within 2 hours of withdrawal from immersion. The final design of the crimped and bonded fittings is shown in Fig. 6, together with a threaded fitting described in the following sections.

<u>As Manufactured kN</u>	<u>Following Environmental Conditioning kN</u>
	23.0
22.1. (Note)	23.8
23.3	24.7
23.3	24.7
23.4	25.2
24.2	25.9
Mean 23.3 S.D. 0.75	Mean 24.6 S.D. 1.0
Note : This fitting pulled off with 70% mixed adhesive failure and 30% cohesive shear failure in the CFRP. All other fittings pulled off 100% cohesively in the CFRP in shear.	

TABLE 1: FAILURE FORCE RESULTS FROM 45 mm OVERLAP CRIMPED AND BONDED BUTT FITTINGS

1) <u>As Manufactured kN</u>	2) <u>Following Environmental Conditioning kN</u>
21.3	(20.8) (Note)
21.4	22.7
21.6	23.1
21.7	23.2
21.8	23.2
22.0	23.5
22.1	23.5
22.2	23.7
Mean 21.8 S.D. 0.3	24.0
	Mean 23.1 S.D. 0.9 (23.4) (0.4)
Note : This fitting failed by pull-off. All other fittings failed by pull out of the central rod and yield and fracture of the alloy tube. Ignoring this atypical result gives the bracketed Mean and S.D. figures.	

TABLE 2: FAILURE FORCE RESULTS FROM 50 mm OVERLAP CRIMPED AND BONDED END FITTINGS

Turned and Threaded Fittings

Most fittings used a bore of 8.1 mm to approximate the desired range of bond line thickness. Some tests into the effect of increasing the bond line thickness were carried out. Fittings with a bore of 8.3 mm failed at less than 75% of the load carried by fittings with an 8.1 mm bore, for the same overlap length.

Except in cases where faulty adherend pre-treatment resulted in a partially or completely adhesive failure (when fittings failed by pulling-off from the CFRP tube) the failure was always cohesive in the CFRP, in shear. The bore of the pulled-off fitting was usually covered completely with a thin black surface layer.

An attempt was made to minimise the weight of the fittings by extending the CFRP tube into the threaded boss, thus reducing overall length. A fitting of this type is shown in Fig. 7, alongside the optimised design ultimately chosen. The former weighs 7g compared with 10g for the latter. However, fittings of this light-weight design exhibited the undesirable behaviour of failing at loads lower than those which they had previously sustained. This behaviour is not yet understood, and the design was abandoned as unsatisfactory.

A brief investigation into the relationship between overlap length and failure force was carried out, as shown in Fig. 8. Based on this data, an overlap length of 45 mm was chosen, and the final fitment designs using this overlap length are shown in Figs. 9 and 10.

The results obtained on these optimum designs are given in Table 3. The male threaded fitments failed by four different failure modes, either fitment pull-off, or the three modes illustrated in Fig. 11. This is thought to indicate a satisfactory, well-balanced design whose precise failure site is probably determined by minor manufacturing differences.

The use of these fittings on another type of CFRP tube was also investigated. The tube is table-rolled from prepreg, and contains 54% by volume of T300 carbon fibres in Fothergill and Harvey Code 95 resin system. The tube was of O.D. 8 mm (nominal), bore 6.3 mm, and the calculated failure force for this tube is approximately 27 kN. The results obtained with this tube are also shown in Fig. 8. The fitments all failed by pull-off from the CFRP tube, the failure being a shear failure of the CFRP in all cases, at loads lower than for the pultruded CFRP tube. Increasing the overlap length to 55 mm improved the loads sustained prior to pull-off, but they could not be considered very satisfactory. (A design load of 25 kN was required, this being the calculated failure force for a rolled tube of 8 mm O.D. and 6.5 mm bore). Shear failure of the CFRP was also observed in pulling-off these longer overlap fittings.

FIG. 8 : Relationship between pull-off load, average bond line shear stress and bond overlap length for 8.1 mm bore fittings mounted on 8 mm o.d. CFRP tube. (N.B. 100% cohesive failure in CFRP tube in all cases).

FIG. 9 : Optimised male threaded fitting, all dimensions mm.

FIG.10 : Optimised female threaded fitting, all dimensions mm.

1) As Manufactured

<u>Fitment Type</u>	<u>Failure Force, kN</u>	<u>Failure Mode</u>
Male	(22.2)	Fitting pull-off (See note)
Female	24.3	"
"	24.4	"
Male	25.2	Fitting failure
"	25.6	Fitting pull-off
"	25.9	Fitting failure
"	26.6	Fitting failure
"	26.7	Fitting pull-off
"	27.0	Fitting pull-off
"	27.1	Fitting failure
	<hr/>	
Mean	25.5	S.D. 1.5
	(25.9)	(1.1)

Note : In this fitting, the bond failure was 50% cohesive in the CFRP and 50% adhesive on the fitting, compared with 100% cohesive failure in the CFRP for all the other fittings in which pull-off occurred. Faulty bonding pre-treatment of the fitting is suspected, and ignoring this result gives the bracketed Mean and S.D. figures.

2) Following Environmental Conditioning (All Male Fitments)

<u>Failure Force kN</u>	<u>Failure Mode</u>
(20.5)	Fitting pull-off (See note)
22.2	"
23.1	"
23.6	"
23.7	"
24.9	"
25.5	"
26.1	Fitting failure in thread
26.5	Fitting pull-off
27.0	Fitting pull-off
	<hr/>
Mean	24.3
	S.D. 2.0
(24.7)	(1.6)

Note : 50% cohesive/50% adhesive failure was observed in this fitting compared with the 100% cohesive failure in the CFRP for all the other fittings in which pull-off occurred. Bracketed figures are as above.

TABLE 3 : RESULTS ON 45 mm OVERLAP THREADED FITTINGS.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The crimping and bonding process shows that lightweight durable fittings can sustain useful loads and can be fabricated from readily available metal bar and tube stock using simple tooling. Careful quality control is essential at the bonding stage to achieve a satisfactorily strong product. The crimped and bonded fittings require longer overlap lengths than turned fittings for a similar load bearing capability. The somewhat lower efficiency of the crimped and bonded joint is doubtless due to the presence of the two adhesive crimp fillets on the joint circumference, producing an effective bond line thickness of about $\frac{1}{2}$ mm at these points. Again, the crimped and bonded overlaps using a high strength aluminium alloy are better than when using a medium strength aluminium alloy. The high strength alloy cracks in the root of the crimp fillet, conforms more closely to the CFRP tube, producing a thinner bond line and a smaller adhesive fillet in the crimp corner. These cracks fill with adhesive during the bonding operation, and could act as potential sites for crevice corrosion, initiation sites for fatigue cracks, and as possible paths for the ingress of water or other environmental substances. Environmental testing of these fittings has demonstrated an improvement in strength, (possibly moisture induced plasticization of the matrix resin or adhesive reducing the effect of stress concentrations in the fitting), and it is not thought that environmental degradation will be a serious problem. The fitting corrosion observed during environmental exposure may have been crevice corrosion, and this factor, together with the fatigue performance, requires further assessment.

The results obtained on the threaded fittings are more amenable to analysis due to the simple cylindrical bond geometry. The failure force data presented in Fig. 8 as a function of bond overlap length, have been computed in terms of the average shear stress on the bond line (assumed 8.0 mm diameter) at failure, when the failure was by pull-off with 100% cohesive failure in shear in the CFRP. It can be seen that the average shear stress at failure remains constant as a function of overlap length for each variety of CFRP tube. Since all other conditions for the fittings were identical, e.g. bond line thickness, geometry, adhesive, surface preparation of adherends and curing schedule, this indicates a fundamental quality difference between the two varieties of CFRP controlling performance. The controlling mechanism for fitment pull-off to occur is interlaminar failure just beneath the surface of the CFRP tube, initiated by the stress concentration at one of the ends of the fitment overlap.

Support to this mechanism is lent by the known behaviour of bonded joints as the overlap length increases. The classical theory in (21) predicts a decrease in the average bond line shear stress as overlap length increases, the magnitude of the shear stress and strain concentration at the overlap ends is substantially unaltered, and all that changes is the length of the lightly loaded region between the stress concentrations. In the coaxial joint bending is negligible, while for the more usual case, out of plane deformations are also occurring (5). The conclusion one draws from the phenomenon observed in this work of a constant average bond line shear stress, is that the failure mechanism is not determined by the behaviour of the adhesive; and the stress and strain concentrations at the ends of the bonded overlap are never high enough to produce failure in the adhesive when the surface bonding pre-treatment was correct.

The interlaminar mode of failure for composites is discussed in (8) with reference to various configurations of flat plate lap joints, which limit the thickness of composite adherends that can be bonded together. The analyses in (8) show that, for lap joints in composite materials the peel stresses are more critical than shear stresses in determining the precise joint geometry required for efficient load transfer; but in the coaxial joint under study, it is difficult to see how peel stresses can be acting to precipitate failure. The conclusions is that the failure mode is almost pure shear in the composite, rather than shear induced by initial cleavage or peel failure as can occur in flat plate lap joints.

Analysis of the shear stresses in a joint with adherends of dissimilar stiffnesses, indicates (8) that the end of the overlap from which extends the less stiff adherend, will be critical for achieving the failure strain of the adhesive.

Although the axial elastic modulus of the CFRP (110 GPa) is higher than that of the aluminium alloy (74 GPa), the greater cross-sectional area of the fitment (required to match fitting and tube strengths) results in a higher stiffness for the fitting than the tube. Thus, the overlap end distant from the threaded boss is predicted to be critical in determining failure due to stiffness imbalance. Since the fittings were manufactured with a chamfered end, as may be seen in Figs. 6, 7 and 11, it is difficult to see what further improvements can be made.

The failure mode observed in this work and in (2) for coaxial joints indicates that the design approach in (6) is not appropriate, and that in (8) and (14) highly questionable. However, the constant bond line failure shear stress in this type of joint suggests a much simpler design route. For any unfamiliar pultrusion, a fitting should be made using any convenient bonded overlap length. Should an interlaminar failure occur on testing, a simple calculation based on the assumption of a critical bond line average shear stress will yield an estimate of the required overlap length to achieve the desired load bearing capability. Thus the data in Fig. 8 indicates that a 62 mm overlap is required to load the rolled tube to the design value of 25 kN. The quoted tensile strength of the CFRP pultrusion is 1.5 GPa; so by assuming that the bond line failure stress will be the same for CFRP hollow and solid sections using the same fibre and matrix resin, one predicts that overlap lengths of 107 mm and 130 mm will be required to load 6.6 mm diameter and 8 mm diameter pultruded CFRP rod respectively to failure.

It is possible that this design method could be applied to any cross section of pultrusion, once initial testing of a section with identical fibre and resin contents has been carried out. The failure mode is apparently being determined by a property related to composite interlaminar shear strength, and this property may be independent of the fitting geometry. The possibility is currently being tested by investigations on larger diameter CFRP tubing.

CONCLUSIONS

A satisfactory technique has been developed for making low cost end-fittings for use on axially loaded pultruded composites, using a combination of crimping and bonding methods. Initial data on these fittings indicate good strength retention following simulated hostile environmental exposure. Weight optimised bonded fittings using conventional machining methods have also been developed. The results on these fittings show that conventional design methods for bonded joints are inappropriate because of the failure mechanism, and a simplified design method is suggested.

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FIG. 1 : Crimping tool and crimped length of alloy tube.

FIG. 2 : Crimped and flattened end fittings.

FIG. 3 : Top - Non optimised threaded end fittings.
Centre - Failure mode of crimped and bonded end fittings.
Bottom - Edge cracking in flattened ends of L105 alloy fittings.

FIG. 4 : Section of crimped and bonded end fitting incorporating central rod. - HT30 Alloy.

FIG. 5 : Section of crimped and bonded butt fitting - L105 alloy.

FIG. 6 : Optimised fittings on pultruded tubing.

FIG. 7 : Optimised threaded fitting and failure mode, with unsuccessful lightweight fitting.

FIG. 11 : Various failure modes for male threaded fittings.